

Analysis of trace levels of toxic *N,N*-dimethylaminopropylamine in alkylamido-betaines by ion-chromatography

N. M. Koshti^{a*}, S. D. Naik^a and N. R. Pai^b

^aGalaxy Research Centre, Galaxy Surfactants Ltd., C-49/2, TTC Industrial Area, Pawne, Navi Mumbai-400 703, India

E-mail : Nirmal.Koshti@galaxysurfactants.com Fax : 91-22-7614507

^bDepartment of Chemistry, D. G. Ruparel College, Mahim, Mumbai-400 018, India

Manuscript received 16 January 2001, revised 3 September 2001, accepted 20 October 2001

Trace levels of *N,N*-dimethylpropyldiamine (DMAPA) in an amphoteric surfactant cocoamidopropylbetaine (CAPB) have been analyzed by cation exchange chromatography. The difficulties associated with liquid/liquid extraction of surfactant matrix from its aqueous solution to isolate DMAPA are overcome by solid phase extraction. The cation exchange mechanism for this diamine is found to be optimum when the ion exchange sites of the separator column are phosphonic acid groups.

Alkyl betaines in general and cocoamidopropylbetaine (CAPB) in particular, are known for their mildness and hence are very widely used in cosmetic industry¹.

CAPB

This tremendously popular cosmetic surfactant invariably has trace levels of free *N,N*-dimethylpropyldiamine (DMAPA) as impurity that is quite toxic². Several procedures for the determination of alkylamines in general have been described in literature³. Nevertheless, there seems to be no convenient procedure for analyzing trace levels of amines especially the ones with short alkyl chain in aqueous surfactant solutions. Hitherto, there is no published procedure for analysis of residual DMAPA in CAPB.

Here, we present a methodology for analyzing DMAPA in surfactant solution using ion-exchange chromatography.

Results and Discussion

After a series of failures with both HPLC (UV-absorbing derivative) and GC (capillary GC with TSD), it was decided to tackle this analytical problem using ion-chromatography since an amine can behave as a cation under acidic conditions and is amenable to ion exchange. Initially, the separator column that was employed (OmniPac PCX-500, Dionex corporation) for analysis of DMAPA had sulfonic acid groups for ion exchange. However, using usual acidic mobile phases, DMAPA could not be eluted in reasonable

retention time. Finally, with the shift from sulfonic acid group to relatively weaker phosphonic acid group on a cation exchanger (Dionex's IonPac CS12A) it was possible to elute the diamine in about 10 min time using either methane sulfonic acid or sulfuric acid solutions. Background conductivity was suppressed by cation self-regenerating suppressor in its autosuppression mode (see Experimental). Analytical calibration curve was established for aqueous DMAPA solutions with concentrations ranging from 1 to 25 ppm.

Isolating traces of DMAPA from the aqueous surfactant solution for subsequent ion chromatography was not an easy task⁴. Although it was possible to extract the surfactant molecules completely into organic phase (*n*-butanol : diethyl ether, 1 : 2), the partial extraction of DMAPA into the organic phase rendered this liquid/liquid extraction unsuitable. The probable reason for this extraction of water-soluble DMAPA into organic phase could be due to the diamine getting trapped inside the 'reverse micelles' of the amphoteric surfactant. Finally, the surfactant extraction without affecting DMAPA recovery was successfully achieved by reusable solid phase extractor (SPE) cartridges (Accubond C-18 reverse phase type from J & W Scientific, USA)⁵.

A commercial CAPB sample (28% active matter along with 5% NaCl) was acidified and diluted five times and passed over C18 bonded solid phase extractor. The filtrate was analyzed using identical chromatographic conditions for aqueous DMAPA solutions where the cation exchanger was IonPac CS12A and mobile phase 20 mM H₂SO₄. The least-square linear regression analysis of the area count versus DMAPA in CAPB obtained by chromatographing spiked

samples over the range 5–25 ppm showed excellent linearity with correlation coefficient of 0.999. Using the standard addition curve, the original CAPB sample was found to have DMAPA content of 3.598 ppm. The replicate analysis (10 measurements) of 5 ppm spiked sample revealed very good accuracy and precision with standard deviation of 0.24 ppm.

A typical chromatogram of DMAPA in CAPB shows a huge signal for Na⁺. Fortunately, under current chromatographic conditions it was possible to separate sodium cation from DMAPA and it was quite evident from spiking experiments that responses for spiked quantities were linear and resolution was not a problem.

In summary, this report describes a methodology using ion exchange chromatography for detecting trace levels of a diamine (lower detection limit of 25 ppb) in the surfactant of commercial importance. Sample preparation by solid phase extraction of surfactant matrix is extremely convenient. The ease of sample preparation coupled with accuracy, sensitivity and reproducibility of the chromatography makes this method useful for routine analysis. This simple and convenient methodology can be extended to other organic cations and anions present in a variety of surfactants. For example, low levels of sulfite ions in alkyl sulfosuccinates⁶ are analyzed using anion exchange chromatography.

Experimental

The ion exchange chromatographic separations were performed on a Dionex DX-500 ion chromatograph equipped with a quaternary gradient pump GP 40 and a conductivity detector CD 20 (Dionex). The eluent path and all other components in direct contact with the eluent were made up of an inert material, polyetheretherketone (PEEK). The cation exchanger IonPac CS12A and Cation Self Regenerating Suppressor CSRS-Ultra were chosen for DMAPA analysis. Star chromatography workstation software (Varian) was used for data processing and quantification.

All HPLC grade solvent (acetonitrile, methanol, isopropanol, cyclohexane, dichloromethane, THF, diethyl ether, *n*-butanol) were used for chromatography, synthesis and extraction. The other reagents and their suppliers were as follows : *N,N*-dimethylpropylamine (BASF), methanesulfonic acid (Qualigens). Commercial cocoamidopropylbetaine was obtained from Galaxy Surfactants Ltd., Mumbai.

Deionized water of the required conductivity (<1.0 μS) was prepared by passing distilled water through cation, anion and mixed bed resin (Indion 225 H, Indion FFIP and Indion MB-6SR all procured from Ion-Exchange (India) Ltd.) and was filtered through 0.45 micron nylon-66 mem-

brane filter (Filtech Pharmalab, Bombay).

Preparation of CAPB samples with solid phase extraction : CAPB (2.0 g) was diluted to 10 ml with 50 mN H₂SO₄. About 5 ml of this solution was then passed through an ODS-Accubond solid phase extraction cartridge (J & W Scientific, USA), then collected in a separate vial and taken for injection into the chromatographic system. Using same commercial CAPB, five spiked samples with 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 ppm of DMAPA were prepared similarly. About 5 ml of all samples were then passed through ODS-Accubond solid phase extraction cartridge and analyzed as per the following chromatographic conditions : cation exchanger : IonPac CS12A, 4 × 250 mm with guard column IonPac CG12A, 4 × 50 mm; mobile phase : 20 mN H₂SO₄; flow rate : 1.0 ml/min; column backpressure : 1230 psi; injection volume ; 100 μL; detection : suppressed conductivity; range : 20 μSFS; background conductivity suppressor : CSRS-Ultra (4 mm) operating in autosuppression external water mode; regenerant for suppressor : water with conductivity 1.6 μS; current supplied for electrolysis of water : 100 mA; background conductivity achieved with suppressor in action : 1–2 μS.

References

- 1 X Domingo in "Amphoteric Surfactants", ed E G Lomax, Surfactant Science Series, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1996, Vol 59, Cosmetic, Toiletry and Fragrance Assoc Inc, Final report on the safety assessment of cocoamidopropylbetaine, *J Am Coll Toxicol*, 1991, 10, 33, J G Weers, J F Rathman, F U Axe, C A Crichlow, L D Foland, D R Scheuing, R J Wiersema and A G Zielske, *Langmuir*, 1991, 7, 854
- 2 "DIN Safety Data Sheet on dimethylpropanediamine", BASF, 1989
- 3 J M Platinga, J J Donkerbroek and R J Mulder, *J Am Oil Chem Soc*, 1993, 70, 97, D C Cullum in "Introduction to Surfactant Analysis", ed D C Cullum, Blackie Academic & Professional, 1994, p 171–191, J W Dinning and J T Stewart, *Talanta*, 1991, 38, 631, P Simon and C Lemacon, *Anal Chem*, 1987, 59, 480, D A Dobberpuhl, J C Hoekstra and D C Johnson, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1996, 322, 55, K Kuwata, E Akiyama, Y Yamazaki, H Yamasaki and Y Kuge, *Anal Chem*, 1983, 55, 2199, T Hamano, Y Mitsuhashi and Y Matsuki, *J Chromatogr*, 1980, 190, 462
- 4 T M Schmitt in "Analysis of Surfactants", ed T M Schmitt, Surfactants Science Series, Marcel Dekker Inc, (1992), Vol 40, p 127
- 5 N Buschmann, A Kruse and R Schultz, *Comun Jorn Com Esp Deterg*, 1992, 23, 317
- 6 S D Naik, M Sc Thesis, University of Mumbai, 2001